

Fixed-mode preregistration for future KNTW LO-HVP window combinations

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Purpose

This preregisters a falsifiable prediction derived from the fixed-direction covariance analysis in the accompanying LO-HVP window audit. It is intended to be publicly timestamped before using any future unblinded KNTW data-driven HVP combination that supplies enough information to reconstruct ID/FULL window-space branch vectors and covariances.

This version adds the public OSF and Zenodo record identifiers. The locked prediction thresholds below are unchanged from version 0.2 dated 13 May 2026.

Locked definitions

Use the RBC/UKQCD-style ID and FULL windows, with ID defined by edges 0.4 fm and 1.0 fm and smoothing $\Delta = 0.15$ fm. For any future KNTW branch/input set, define $\mathbf{x}_i = (\mathbf{a}_{\mu}^{\text{ID}}, \mathbf{a}_{\mu}^{\text{FULL}})$. Define CMD-3 as the branch/sub-combination containing CMD-3 pi+pi- input; define rest as the corresponding non-CMD-3 public pi+pi- branch set included by KNTW. The KNTW default covariance convention is primary.

Primary reconstruction

Construct the between-input covariance matrix in the (ID,FULL) plane. Here μ_{CMD3} and μ_{rest} are the (ID,FULL) branch vectors of the CMD-3 input and the inverse-variance-weighted mean of the non-CMD-3 inputs in the KNTW combination. Let \mathbf{u}_{all} be the leading eigenvector, with sign fixed so that it points toward $\mu_{\text{CMD3}} - \mu_{\text{rest}}$. Compute $\cos(\theta)$ between \mathbf{u}_{all} and $\mu_{\text{CMD3}} - \mu_{\text{rest}}$. Then remove CMD-3 while holding \mathbf{u}_{all} fixed and compute

$$R_{\text{noCMD3}} = \mathbf{u}_{\text{all}}^T \Sigma_{\text{between}}^{\text{noCMD3}} \mathbf{u}_{\text{all}} / (\mathbf{u}_{\text{all}}^T \Sigma_{\text{between}}^{\text{all}} \mathbf{u}_{\text{all}}).$$

Primary predictions

Confirmed if both hold:

1. Alignment: $\cos(\theta) \geq 0.97$.
2. Leave-one-out collapse: $R_{\text{noCMD3}} \leq 0.50$.

Strongly confirmed if $\cos(\theta) \geq 0.99$ and $R_{\text{noCMD3}} \leq 0.35$.

Falsified if $\cos(\theta) < 0.90$ or $R_{\text{noCMD3}} > 0.75$ under KNTW's default covariance scenario.

Strongly falsified if $\cos(\theta) < 0.80$ or $R_{\text{noCMD3}} > 0.85$.

Secondary predictions

Where bin-level information is available, the 0.70–0.80 GeV band should carry at least 35% of the fixed-mode bin attribution. As a negative control, removing any single non-CMD-3 branch should not produce a larger fixed-direction variance collapse than removing CMD-3.

Notes

The thresholds are deliberately looser than the current public-data central values. The point is to test whether the leading ID/FULL covariance mode remains CMD-3-aligned under an independent future combination and covariance convention, not to reproduce the last digit of the present implementation.

References

Keshavarzi, Nomura, Teubner and Wright, arXiv:2409.02827.

Keshavarzi, Nomura, Teubner and Wright, arXiv:2604.25004.